

LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF PLANT FIBRE REINFORCED HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper experimentally studied the low-velocity impact behaviors of jute/ramie fibre fabric reinforced hybrid composites with the aim of investigation on the effect of hybrid ratios on impact performance and energy absorption of the composites. A range of impact energies varied from 2 J to 20 J were employed on five composites including jute fibre reinforced composite, ramie fibre reinforcement composite and three hybrid composites. The impact resistance of jute fibre reinforced composite and energy absorption capacity of ramie fibre reinforced composites were improved with hybridizing this two fibre fabric together. The damage area were evaluated with an ultrasonic C-scan instrument. Results indicate that hybrid laminates with volume fraction of ramie fibre at 55% have better impact energy absorption capability and enhanced impact resistance with respect to the all-jute laminates. Hybridizing jute and ramie fibers together will be an effective method of solving the problem of lacking rigidity of jute fibre reinforced composite and the high price of ramie fibre reinforced composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Demand for greater weight saving and impact protection employing lightweight materials. There is a growing interest in the properties of cellular materials for their use in impact energy absorbing structures. However, one of the major problems that should be solved before extensively using the natural cellular materials in energy absorbing systems is the understanding of their behaviours during impact process. A number of investigations have been carried out to assess the potential of natural fibres as reinforcement in polymers, some comparative studies between laminates reinforced with different species of natural fibres and polymers have been published [1-3].

For many years, there has been a growing interest in the properties of hybrid composites such as those formed by combining different types of fibres or different laminating materials [4, 5]. Naik et al. [6] have investigated impact behavior and post impact compressive characteristics of glass-carbon/epoxy hybrid composites with alternate stacking sequences. Sarasini et al [7] studied the impact behaviour of woven hybrid basalt-carbon/epoxy composites. Results indicate that hybrid laminates with intercalated configuration have better impact energy absorption capability and enhanced damage tolerance, while hybrid laminates with sandwich-like configuration present the most favourable flexural behaviour. Suresh Kumar et al [8] found hemp-basalt/epoxy hybrid composites have better residual flexural strength and impact properties compared to non-hybrid composites. Therefore, good design on hybrid composites can combine the advantages of various fibres and enhance the overall performance of the composite. Moreover, it can also prevent matrix cracking and improve the fracture toughness of the composites.

The aim of this study is the investigation of the low-velocity impact behaviour of all plant fibre-ramie/jute hybrid laminates by taking into account the effect of hybrid ratio. Woven ramie-jute/epoxy hybrid composites were fabricated in sandwich-like hybrid structures and subjected to low-velocity impact using a drop weight apparatus.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Ramie plain fabrics and jute plain fabrics were supplied by Hunan Huasheng Dongting Ramie Textile Co.,Ltd and Anji Zhengxing Fabric Co.,Ltd, respectively. The basic parameters of ramie and jute fabrics are listed in Table 1. Epoxy resin E51, together with MeTHPA curing agent and DMP-30 tertiary amine accelerator were supplied by Shanghai Zhongsi Industry Co., Ltd.

	Ramie fabric	Jute fabrics
Weave	Plain	Plain
Areal density (g/m ²)	255.6	116.7
Warp yarns (yarns/dm)	205	52
Weft yarns (yarns/dm)	228	58
Filament diameter (μm)	15.93	35.68

Table 1: Basic parameters of ramie and jute fabrics

2.2 Composites fabrication

The ramie and jute fabric were preimpregnated with the mixed epoxy resin by hand lay-up process. The ramie/jute fabric reinforced epoxy laminates were manufactured by stacking the appropriate number of preregs in a picture-frame mould (typically 350×300 mm²), and preheated in hot-press machine at the temperature of 90 °C with a pressure of 1 MPa for one hour to ensure good wetting, then cured at 120 °C with a pressure of 6 MPa for two hours. Following processing, the panel was allowed to cool slowly in the press. Five types of composites with different hybrid ratios shown in Table 2 were produced to investigate the effect of hybrid ratio on the impact properties of the composites which included one jute fiber reinforced polymer composite (JFRP), 3 types of ramie/jute fiber reinforced hybrid polymer composites and one ramie fiber reinforced polymer composite (RFRP). The fiber volume fractions of ramie and jute in the composites were varying while the total fiber volume fractions of the composites were kept the same, which were approximately 50%. Fabrics are stacked as a sandwich-like sequence with ramie fibre layers (skins) and jute fibre layers (core) for composites with three hybrid ratios. The thickness of the laminates were 4.15 ± 0.08 mm.

Designation	Volume fraction ratio V _r % (Ramie/Jute)	Ply number ratio (Ramie/Jute)	Stacking sequence
JFRP	0/100	0/8	[J] ₈
6R6J	30/70	6/6	[R ₃ /J ₆ /R ₃]
12R4J	55/45	12/4	[R ₆ /J ₄ /R ₆]
18R2J	80/20	16/2	[R ₉ /J ₂ /R ₉]
RFRP	100/0	22/0	[R] ₂₂

Table 2: Different hybrid ratios of five types of hybrid composites.

Figure 1: Comparison of (a) ramie fabric and (b) jute fabric in macroscopic scale.

2.2 Low-velocity impact test

A series of low-velocity impact tests were conducted on the plant fibre fabric reinforced composite laminates in order to investigate their impact performance as well as the damage mechanisms according to ASTM D7136. The low-velocity impact tests were conducted on laminates using an INSTRON CEAST 9350 drop-weight tower. A hemispherical steel indenter was attached to the impactor and with a diameter of 16 mm, the total mass of the impactor was 2.4 kg. The samples were placed on a steel support with a cut out of 75×50 mm² and were clamped on four corners. The anti-rebound system of INSTRON CEAST 9350 can catch the crosshead and preventing it from hitting the sample a second time. The load–time traces during a test were recorded with the computer. In order to evaluate damage area, the impacted specimens were inspected with an ultrasonic C-scan instrument (NAUT21, JAPAN PROBE).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Morphology of ramie and jute fibres

The general physical and mechanical properties of ramie and jute fibres were given in Table 3. Actually, owing to the naturally growing characteristics of plant and extracting from different parts of plants, various species of plant fibres displays distinguishing physical and mechanical properties. In addition, microstructures of plant fibers are quite complicated and unique that each kind of plant fiber has its own characteristics. It can be found from Table 3 and Figure 2 that the microstructure of the plant fibres play a significant role in their mechanical properties besides their chemical composition, such as fibre diameter, porosity and cell numbers. In Figure 2, the cross section of ramie fibre shows a single cell structure. However, jute fibre shows multi-scale structures. The distinct cross-section areas and geometrical parameters leads to various mechanical properties of different plant fibres.

Fibre	Length (mm)	Diameter (μm)	Cell Number	Porosity (%)	Cellulose (%)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Price (Yuan /kg)
Ramie	50-152	20-35	1	5-8	65-70	400~938	3.6-3.8	7.2
Jute	2-4	30-109	3-50	7-9	57-60	393~773	1.5-1.8	2.6

Table 3: The properties and price of ramie and jute fibres [9].

Figure 2: Microstructure of (a) ramie and (b) jute fibres.

3.2 The impact response of JFRP and RFRP

Figure 3 shows typical force–time histories following impact tests on JFRP and RFRP panels with impact energy ranged from 2 J to 20 J. It can be seen from Figures 3 (a) and (b) that some initial oscillations are apparent in the curves, which are probably due to ringing inside the load cell and dynamic effects in the plate. The figures show that increasing the impact energy results in increasing in the impact force and the impact duration before being perforated. It can be seen from Figure 4 (a) that the JFRP laminate was perforated at 20 J without showing any energy recovery. However, the displacements return toward the axis origin during unloading for RFRP laminates at four impact energies, suggesting that some elastic energy is recovered. JFRP absorb more energy through higher overall deformation and being more compliant.

Figure 5 shows the different damage patterns and structural responses of JFRP and RFRP laminates tested at increasing impact energies. Penetration of the indenter through the laminate thickness was accompanied by big cracks, fibre breakage were observed on JFRP composites following an impact test of 20 J. In the same impact condition, RFRP composites exhibit cross-shaped cracks with associated matrix cracking but without evidence of penetration, this suggesting that RFRP composites process superior impact resistance compare to JFRP.

Figure 3: Typical load vs. time curves for (a) JFRP and (b) RFRP following different impact energies.

Figure 4: Typical load vs. deformation curves for (a) JFRP and (b) RFRP following different impact energies.

Figure 5: Photos of damage progression on front and rear faces of JFRP and RFRP.

3.3 Effect of hybrid ratios on impact properties of composites

It can be seen from Figure 6 that with increase the volume fraction ratio of ramie fibre up to 55% (12R4J), laminates exhibit a residual elastic response following an impact energy of 20 J. The effect of hybrid ratio on the impact properties of ramie/jute fibre reinforced hybrid composites was shown in Figure 7. The maximum impact force increased with the increasing of the relative volume content of ramie fibers as shown in Figure 7(a), indicating greater load bearing ability of the laminates at higher V_r levels. RFRP laminates exhibit a lower displacement, whilst JFRP and hybrid laminates, being more compliant, absorb energy through the global deformation. It can be seen from Figure 7(b) that JFRP and hybrid laminates absorb more energy compare to RFRP through higher overall deformation, fibre breakage and splitting. Three hybrid laminates show similar energy absorption capacity to the RFRP composites following impact energy up to 14 J. However, the hybrid composite show superior energy absorption ability compare to the RFRP when impact with an energy of 20 J, the absorbed energy of 6R6J (V_r % =30%) even higher than JFRP. It can be seen from Figure 8 that 6R6J laminate was also perforated following an impact energy of 20 J. The breakage of ramie fibres in the hybrid

composite dissipated more energy than that of in JFRP laminate. In fact, it can be seen from Figure 8 that the damaged area for 12R4J laminates is the smallest among five composites, suggesting that volume fraction ratio of ramie fiber is 55% (12J4R) is the optimized hybrid ratio for the ramie/jute hybrid composites.

Figure 6: Force and displacement traces of five type of composites

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Bar chart of (a) Maximum force vs. Impact energy and (b) Absorbed energy vs. Impact energy.

Figure 8: Damage area vs. Impact energy bar chart of five composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of ramie/jute fibre hybridization on low velocity impact response of ramie/jute fabric reinforced epoxy composites have been experimentally investigated. Three different hybrid ratio

laminates have been prepared: the volume fraction of ramie were 30%, 55% and 80%. Impact damage at comparable energy levels, causes penetration of the jute laminates whereas hybrid laminates and ramie laminates show cross-shaped cracks on the front face but without evidence of penetration. Ramie and jute fibre hybridization prevents penetration in all-jute composite and low ramie volume fraction hybrid laminates while enhancing the peak forces compared to jute laminates. Ramie/jute volume fraction of 55/45 was the optimized hybrid ratio for this type of hybrid composites.

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